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Life from Death

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Abstract

Life after death is a belief that's held by cryogenic agencies. The believe that one-day the dead will be brought back to live. I hypothesize that by following specific biomedical procedures it can be possible to revive biological beings after all biological processes have ceased in them. By referencing to past discoveries in neuronal conduction after death specifically Luigi Galvani's famous experiment which made a dead frog twitch, as well as the discovery of Anastasis I came up with a chain of procedures which in theory will make it possible to bring biological beings back from the dead. This study aims to resuscitate [at a cellular level as well as physiological] biological beings after all biological processes have ceased in them.

Keywords: Anastasis, apoptosis, galvanic battery, cryogenic agencies, biological

Introduction

In 2007 two scientists [Ho Man Holly Tang and Ho Lam Hogan Tang] proved that it's possible for animal cells to recover from apoptosis even after DNA damage and cell fragmentation. The process of cells recovering from apoptosis which they discovered they named Anastasis. They firstly experimented with human cancer cells, this asking the question whether cells can recover from apoptosis. They exposed the cancer cells to toxins and waited for the exposed cells to die. Next they washed the apoptotic cells and incubated them with fresh media overnight, the cells recovered when they were observed the following morning [Charles 2019] ^[4]. In 2009 scientist only new of 12 caspases in humans and 10 in mice, though the role of this enzymes in apoptosis was determined in 1993. Today there about 13 known caspases. Caspases are always present and observed during the process of apoptosis. Caspases are a family of proteases enzymes [Cohen 1997] ^[5]. In the late 1700s an Italian physiologist named Luigi Galvani conducted an experiment were he connected a lightning rod to a dead frog just about a storm occurrence and waited for the storm to arrive. When the storm finally came and lightning flushed nearby the frog twitched. After Volter published his work on bi-metal electricity the notion

of reanimation come in to the thoughts of the public in the 1800s [Andrew 2017] ^[1]. Apoptosis causes the cell of a biological being to go through certain changes both mothological and biochemical. Cells going through the stages of apoptosis display cell blabbing, DNA fragmentation as well as nuclear fragmentation. Apoptosis is activated by either an intrinsic pathway or an extrinsic pathway. The intrinsic pathway results from when the cell senses stress, mitochondria leak certain apoptotic activation proteins which bind to form a molecule called an Apoptosome.

The Apoptosome then releases protosea enzymes called caspases which clive to the DNA as well as cytoskeleton of the cell and damaging them. The extrinsic pathway is when a cell going through the process of apoptosis leaks apoptotic molecules such as caspases to neighbouring cells. The apoptotic molecules bind to death receptors of the cell which are located on the cell membrane and starting the process of apoptosis in that cell [Brown 2014] ^[3].

Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) is a clear Wight liquid secreted from the ventricles of the brain in to the subarachnoid space. CSF is found on the surface of the brain and spinal cord and in the brain ventricles [Anne, Kathleen, & Wilson, 1996] ^[2]. Neurons in their resting membrane action potential state

have an equal charge on both sides of the neuronal membrane [Sheeba, Gu, Sharma 2008] ^[7]. In the resting state a nerve or neuron is polarised such that the inside is negative while the outside is positive. During stimulation an impulse or action potential flows along the neuron where sodium ions flood in to the cell while potassium ions flood out of the cell. The exchange of sodium ions in to the neuron and potassium ions out of the neuron only happens at the axon of the nerve cell and not the myelin sheath [Anne, Kathleen, & Wilson, 1996] ^[2].

Chest compressions is a process were by a person's heart is compressed frequently for a period of time to manually circulate blood around the body because the heart has stopped pumping blood around the body automatically. Chest compressions can restart the heart again and get it to pump blood around the body automatically again [Pichereau 2015] ^[6]. This study aims to resuscitate biological beings after all biological processes have ceased in them.

Materials and Methods section

I have 3 thoughts of how to sustain an action potential in a deceased biological being and to revive them. The first way would be to actually attach an electromagnetic emitting device to the cranial cavity of the biological being. The device would be made water proof by laminating it's outside with a polymer (plastic). This is because the device would be submerged in the cerebrospinal fluid. The device would be so thin that it would not touch the cerebral cortex of the biological being. This method requires the biological being's cranial cavity to be enclosed after attaching the device. Clinically the patient now has increased intracranial pressure after the cranial with the device attached is enclosed. Hopefully the increased intracranial pressure caused by inserting the device to the cranial cavity of the patient doesn't hinder the blood flow to the brain or the action potential.

Using this method the heat shock protein would be administered in to the blood stream after inserting the device. The device will receive a signal that activates it after the heat shock protein is administered and the cells of the patient have recovered. The most basic design of such a device is as follows. The case of the design is metallic, probably steel. The case will have a built in compartment meant to store positively charged ions. This compartment will have an insulator material glued to the walls of the compartment. A different metal from that of the case will be submerged into the positive ions. This metal will be attached to another different metal that coils around another metal.

This coiling metal will be attached to 3 different metals. The first metal that the coiling metal will be attached to is the one submerged into the positive ions. The second metal will be the metal that it coils around and the third metal will be the one that carries the flow of electrons into the patient's head. The metal that carries the flow of electrons into the patient's head will actually protrude from the patient's head. This will actually help with the increased intracranial pressure induced by the electromagnetic emitting device in the patient by releasing some of the displaced cerebrospinal fluid. Back to the design of the device. The metal that protrudes out of the patient's head will have lengthen split ends to hold the device at the needed height in the

subarachnoid space and the lengthen split ends stabilized. The protruding metal will also have a plastic raping around it.

The protruding metal will then be exposed to an electromagnetic field. This should cause electrons to flow from the protruding metal to the metal submerged in the positively charged ions. For a more complementation to the Galvanic battery the protruding metal can be made long enough that it will be possible to submerge the metal in negatively charged ions in a container on the flow. The container will have a semi-permeable membrane were the one side of the container has negative ions and the other positive ions, this is to allow for the redox reaction to occur more controllably. Another design of the device is that two metals will be submerged in ions (one metal in positive ions and the other in negative ions separated by a semi-permeable membrane). This two metals will extend into the patient's head where they are coil around perhaps three metals lying parallel to the crown of the skull or somewhere around the tentorium cerebelli and lateral venous sinus, since that place has a wider space. The two metals will be joined where they coil around the numerous metals. The metals that extend into the head of the patient will be laminated in plastic until for where they coil.

The plastic raping will be a thin lamination so that the electromagnetic pulse can penetrate through. After the patient is fully revived the device can then be removed from the patient's head. The hole(s) left in the person's skull can then be sealed, possibly by placing a metal plate in the patient's cranial cavity. The wound(s) in the patient's muscle tissue can then be given time to heal. Simultaneously while the device is active cardiopulmonary resuscitation [CPR] should be performed at this stage to try and revive the patient. The second method I have is to pump blood containing nutrients, oxygen to the patient's head while their brain is exposed to an electromagnetic pulse and the patient is seat up instead of lying down. The nutrients, oxygen are pumped with enough pressure that they flow against the electromagnetic pulse. The electromagnetic pulse is so great that the nutrients, oxygen ionise.

Then the ionised nutrients, oxygen is released into the subdural space and exchanged to the neurons of the brain and shifting the charge gradient of the neuron. CPR should be administered before 10 minutes after the charge gradient is shifted with the patient seating at least 135 degrees to try and revive the person. Or while the electromagnetic pulse is active CPR is simultaneously performed with the patient siting at least 135 degrees with no need to ionize nutrients, oxygen.

How the action potential is restarted?

After death of a human the cells them self-die. Unlike spinal cord damage were the type of cell death is necrosis, after death the cells in humans and other biological beings commit suicide programmatically and this is known as apoptosis. The action potential in neurons after death is still present though held in its resting membrane action potential state. An introduction of 2 different types of metals joined together in the neuron will cause an action potential to flow through the neuron and the biological being contract their muscles [after death]. The clinical condition known as brain death is particularly challenging to this study since there are

no signs of blood flow to the brain of patients declared as brain dead, or any activity in the brain. Brain death is caused by some sort of condition blocking the blood from flowing to the brain. For patients who died from brain death to be considered as part of the trail the condition causing the blockage firstly has to be removed surgically, after death. The study does not aim to fix necrotic cells as that is particularly a different topic.

Even after a person dies and the cells have committed suicide it's still possible to pump blood around their body. Chest compressions will make it possible for blood to be pumped around a dead person's body but firstly blood has to be introduced in to the body. It can be expressed as there being a wanting of ions to flow from one side of the neuronal membrane to the other, due to one side being more positive than the other. The wanting is stronger in life beings than cadavers. because the electrons in different metals move towards the neuron at different rates, due to different concentrations and or sizes of gas atoms in the two metals and the neuron caring a positive charge, when an instrument such as a galvanic battery is used with the ions in the neuron being used as the charges of the battery where the two metals are put, this increases the action potential in the neuron after death. If the voltage caused by the metals placed in the neuron is great enough an action potential occurs after death. The same principal as in the above sentence is considered in this study. This study aims primarily to start an action potential in the brain after death.

The method considered to start the action potential is by firstly opening the persons cranial and then exposing their brain to an electromagnetic field [following the two methods described in the materials and methods section]. The magnetic field should act the same way as the conducting metals in a sense and this sense is by increasing the voltage in the neuron by making one side more negative than the other; kind of like electro cutting the biological being.

Significance of the heat shock protein

When the process of depolarization and repolarisation is re-initiated the question amounts to wherever the cells in the biological being will be able to reverse apoptosis and fix the apoptotic cells in the biological being? The answer is yes! With an introduction of a heat shock protein into the cell, the cells will be able to repair themselves through a process called Anastasis. Significant to this study is the reversal of late stage apoptosis. Very late, so much so that it's after the stage were the cell divides. At this stage, after revival of the biological being, they can be treated to chemo therapy if irregular cell growth is detected. The steps to the procedure will be firstly the introduction of the heat shock protein into the cells of the biological being, this can be done by mixing the protein in to the blood supply of the biological being and pumping it around the body by giving the biological being chest compressions. Quickly after the recovery of the cells the brain of the biological being should be exposed to the electromagnetic pulse to initiate the action potential.

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